

Negative Emissions: A new phase of climate policy to reduce global warming to 1 °C above pre-industrial levels

(Version 1.0, English, 6 June 2024)

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This is a translation of the German language peer reviewed publication: Tremmel et al. (2024). doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10828229. The translation was not separately reviewed.

Suggested citation: Tremmel, J., Steinberger, B., Linow, S., Breyer, C., Gerhards, C., Vollmer, D., Zens, J., Fichter, C., Masurenko, C. (2024). Negative Emissions: A new phase of climate policy to reduce global warming to 1 °C above pre-industrial levels. Diskussionsbeiträge der Scientists for Future, 16, 1-39. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11493905

Summary

The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change's new synthesis report projects that it is unlikely that it will be possible to limit global warming to 1.5 °C. The latest scientific findings on tipping points also show that irreversible changes to the Earth system are highly likely to occur if the atmospheric CO₂ content already reached today is not reduced to a lower level. In terms of quantity, a reduction in the atmospheric CO₂ concentration from today's around 424 ppm to 350 ppm is necessary. The value of 350 ppm would correspond to a warming of around 1 °C compared to the pre-industrial value of 280 ppm.

Politically determined targets should be adapted to the progress of scientific knowledge. International determinations and concrete steps towards this 1 °C target should be taken annually. This would be a new phase in climate policy in which, in addition to the primary goal of avoiding all greenhouse gas emissions, the secondary goal of quickly achieving negative emissions before 2050 would be added as a second branch of the global climate strategy. This secondary goal must under no circumstances – including from a financial perspective – affect the efforts to reduce emissions which need to be reinforced. While the state must set the framework conditions, non-state actors also have an important role to play in financing negative emissions.

Scaling up the CO₂ extraction and storage (sequestration) approaches to the necessary scale in the near future is an ambitious but not utopian goal. Plant-based CO₂ extractions will play an important role but cannot handle the volume required. The inexpensive availability of renewable energies in many places around the world increasingly enables the use of technological approaches despite their high energy requirements. In addition to climate-ethical aspects (with consequences for the financial viability of this approach), the physical and technical feasibility are discussed in this article. The permanent storage of CO₂ in the geological subsoil is considered comparatively safe and there is sufficient capacity, e. g. in porous formations. The safest option is to store it in the formations in which the CO₂ mineralizes. Technologies for capturing the gas include especially direct air capture (DAC) and – with limitations – bioenergy carbon capture and sequestration (BECCS). In addition, accelerated weathering and afforestation (even without BECCS) and carbon accumulation in soils or moors could make substantial contributions. The biodiversity crisis also requires large areas for species protection that can also be used for biological CO₂ removal. The German Carbon Dioxide Storage Act is no longer up to date in this new phase of climate policy because it prohibits the transport and storage of CO₂.

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1. Introduction: Time is of the essence!

Global warming is endangering a safe and dignified life for a large part of humanity. In the period of 10 000 years shown in Fig. 1, it becomes clear how extraordinary the increase in CO₂ emissions has been in human history since the Neolithic Revolution, i. e. when humanity became sedentary.

Fig. 1: Change in CO₂ concentration in the atmosphere over the last 10 000 years (Scripps Institution of Oceanography, 2024, CC BY 4.0). The unit of measurement for CO₂ concentration, ppm or parts per million, can be illustrated like this: You can imagine the Earth's atmosphere as a room filled with a million spheres. Most of them are light and dark grey oxygen and nitrogen molecules. There are also a few red CO₂ molecules floating in this room. In pre-industrial times there were about 280, now there are about 424. Despite their small number, CO₂ molecules are responsible for global warming.

The current CO₂ concentration is higher than at any other epoch in the last two million years (IPCC, 2023, 4). Throughout Earth's history, CO₂ concentration and Earth's mean temperature are closely correlated. During the period of more than half a million years shown in Fig. 2, the Milanković cycles – periodic changes in Earth's orbital parameters – were the original cause of the temperature fluctuations (e. g. Ganopolski et al., 2016).¹ However, these were increased by changes in CO₂ concentration. This means that the causal connection between CO₂ concentration and temperature changes is also proven in the history of the earth (Archer, 2016).

Indeed, the CO₂ concentration in the atmosphere is far above the concentration that occurs at its maximum in interglacial periods. It continues to increase, and the increase in concentration is occurring more and more quickly: in the 1970s, the annual average increase was 0.7 ppm/year. In the 1980s the growth rate was 1.6 ppm/year; in the 1990s 2.2 ppm/year (Latif, 2020, 55-66). There is currently an increase of around 2.6 ppm per year (Scripps Institution of Oceanography, 2024).

¹ The background is the fluctuation of solar radiation in summer, usually based on 65° N as a reference value.

Fig. 2: Relationship between CO₂ in ppm and temperature changes in Earth's history. (Bildungsserver Wiki, n.d., data basis: Uemura et al., 2018, License: CC BY 4.0).

As a result, sea levels are rising faster and faster every decade (IPCC 2023, 5). Sea level rise has doubled from 22.7 mm in 1993-2002 to 46.2 mm in 2013-2022 (World Meteorological Organization, 2023). This finding is deeply discouraging. A good thirty years after the first IPCC report was published and 27 climate conferences (COPs) later, humanity has not managed to slow down or even reverse the dangerous development. If you compare the climate crisis to humanity driving in a fog towards a cliff, the speed at which we are approaching that cliff is accelerating. We know that this is ahead of us, but not exactly how far it is to the cliff. Since the beginning of the Industrial Revolution, the concentration of the trace gas CO₂ has increased almost exponentially, from 280 ppm before 1850 to around 424 ppm in May 2023 (Scripps Institution of Oceanography, 2024).

Explanation box 1:

There are various metaphors for climate change. A good metaphor is that of a child wrapped in a layered wool blanket. This blanket is made up of many superimposed, very thin layers of wool. Usually, the blanket was made up of 28 such layers, and the child is used to it and feels comfortable. As more layers were gradually added, it became too warm for the child, but up to 35 layers it was still bearable. There have now been 42 shifts and the child is at risk of heat stroke if this continues over the long term. The layers are the newly added CO₂ emissions. We must stop adding layers around the child (i.e. the surface of the Earth) as soon as possible. At the same time, it was previously considered impossible or too expensive to remove a few layers. These would be the negative emissions.

Other greenhouse gases can also be easily integrated into this metaphor. While around 15 to 40 percent of CO₂ emissions are still left in the atmosphere after 1000 years, methane, for example, only has a residence time of around ten years, after which it dissolves into CO₂ and water. Within the metaphor, you can imagine this as a blanket layer, which this time is not made of wool, but of a material that transforms into a material that is much less thick

Certain processes have resulted in linear increases in CO₂, such as the conversion of forest into pasture. Other processes, e. g. the thawing of permafrost or the destruction of the Amazon rainforest through droughts or forest fires, can lead to self-reinforcing increases in CO₂ and other greenhouse gases in the atmosphere (cf. Kemp et al., 2022: 9; Steffen et al., 2018, 8255f; Tollefson, 2022). Such self-reinforcing elements of the climate system are also called tipping elements; The points from which changes are irreversible are called tipping points. The tipping element *Greenland Ice Sheet* should be considered as an example: A large part of the surface of the approx. 2 400 000 billion t of ice is above 2000 m above sea level, part of it is above 3000 m. The high-rising part of a glacier is the area in which new ice forms, which then flows down with the glacier. At these altitudes the air temperature is significantly colder than at sea level, as the temperature decreases by 6 – 9 °C for every 1000 m difference in altitude. If this feeding area of the glacier decreases, it begins to shrink disproportionately faster, because when large masses of ice begin to melt due to rising surface temperatures, the upper layers eventually no longer reach into the cold air layers in which they are currently located. They will therefore melt over the course of a few centuries even after the global surface temperature stabilizes.²

Exceeding even a single tipping point carries the risk of setting off a cascade that causes a new “hot period” on Earth that is unfavourable for the species *Homo sapiens* (Steffen et al., 2018; Lenton et al., 2019, 594). For example, if the Amazon rainforest were to disappear (tipping point 1), the greenhouse gases stored there would quickly enter the earth's atmosphere (through fire or rotting biomass). The resulting increase in the greenhouse effect can then accelerate the thawing of permafrost, which stores large amounts of methane and carbon dioxide, in the Arctic (tipping point 2). This in turn could trigger further tipping points. As a consequence, the ecological niche in which humans or even land vertebrates can live is shrinking as more and more regions permanently or at least temporarily exceed the tolerable temperature during the year (Powis et al., 2023). Ultimately, human life will be threatened there. Against this background, McKinnon (2009, 190) argues for the application of a strong prudence principle: action is necessary and justified even in the face of uncertainty and insufficient information about possible harm, “because the worst consequences of not taking precautionary action are worse than the worst consequences of taking precautionary action, and choosing the former course of action is not consistent with treating present and future people as equals ...”

Current scientific publications (Breyer et al., 2023; Hansen et al., 2008; Hansen et al., 2017; Richardson et al., 2023; Rockström et al., 2023) show that irreversible catastrophic effects are possible if the CO₂ concentration exceeds 350 ppm (or 1 °C temperature warming above pre-industrial levels) over a longer period of time.³ At the moment, the CO₂ concentration is already about 74 ppm higher than 350 ppm. Therefore, the goal of the global community must be to achieve this value again. In other

² Added to this are the seasons: ice that melts in summer is replaced less and less in winter.

³ It must be taken into account that any limit value for a CO₂ concentration must also include other greenhouse gases (as CO₂ equivalent). In the industrial sector, this primarily applies to methane, fluorinated and chlorinated hydrocarbons and SF₆ as well as methane and nitrous oxide from land use.

words: Humanity must reverse the global warming that has already occurred to around +1.2 °C by about 0.2 °C (as of 2023). This requires decisive action in the next few years. Climate damage recorded by reinsurance companies has been rising sharply for several years now. That's why it's in our interest to break through the fatal “business as usual” and end the fossil era as quickly as possible.

What's more: the course that will determine the path of the Earth's climate system for centuries will be set in one direction or the other in the next few years (maximum two to three decades). One can therefore speak of the “urgency of the long view”, i.e. we must act very quickly in order to influence climate conditions in the further future. We have a moral obligation to future generations to maintain safe planetary boundaries, i.e. to avoid existential risks. Emotionally, we may only feel responsible for the world and the path to it in a period of time that our children and grandchildren will experience for themselves. A child who starts school today has a good chance of experiencing the world in the year 2100 and the path there. But there is no reason to give lower weight to the generations that will live after 2100 than the people who will live until then (Tremmel, 2012). It is therefore important to also take the time after 2100 into account. This still happens too rarely, even in IPCC reports (Kemp et al., 2022). In the IPCC's AR6 synthesis report, for the first time, there is a life-course-related impact of rising temperatures on different generations, pointing out that the heat problems for later generations will continue to increase even after 2100 if we act as weakly today as we have done so far (see Fig. 3).

Atmospheric CO₂ is very stable, therefore the above-mentioned increasing concentration of CO₂ in the atmosphere corresponds to an unchecked quantitative increase in greenhouse gases. Fig. 4 shows all emissions of all relevant greenhouse gases since the beginning of industrialization.

Fig. 3: How different generations are affected (IPCC, 2023, Fig. SPM. 1 (c), p. 7).

Historical GHG emissions

CLIMATEWATCH

Data source: PIK; Location: World; Sectors/Subsectors: Total excluding LULUCF; Gases: KYOTOGHG; Calculation: Total; Show data by Gases.

Fig. 4: Annual global emissions of relevant greenhouse gases in CO₂ equivalents. Since, for example, CH₄ is broken down in the atmosphere, its warming potential decreases over time. Here, an average of 100 years is used to convert to CO₂ equivalents. LULUCF (land use, land use change and forestry) are excluded (ClimateWatch, 2022; data source: Gütschow et al. (2016); Gütschow & Pflüger (2022); license: CC BY-4.0).

Since the first IPCC assessment report was presented in 1990, global climate policy aimed at avoiding CO₂ has been unable to bring about a turnaround. The accelerated expansion of renewable energies and the necessary behavioural changes are most likely no longer even enough to meet the 1.5 °C target. Recent scientific findings assume that the tipping point for the Greenland ice sheet is somewhere between 0.8 °C and 3 °C, so in the worst case it has already been exceeded (Lenton, 2021; Armstrong McKay et al, 2022). The Gulf Stream is threatening to weaken, and the tropical rainforest is in danger of turning from a CO₂ sink into a source (Doughty et al., 2023). In summary, humanity is most likely much closer to the tipping points than climate science expected for 2023 a few decades ago.

The increasingly precise knowledge about climatic connections requires a reassessment of the situation: Politically set targets should be adapted to the progress of scientific knowledge. In Germany, the Federal Constitutional Court also emphasized this in its climate ruling.⁴ Internationally, the limit on temperature rise agreed in the Paris Climate Protection Agreement of 2015 (European Union, 2016) of well below 2 °C,

⁴ "... Article 20a of the German Constitution imposes on the legislature a permanent obligation to adapt environmental law to the latest developments and findings in science. If the temperature target agreed in Article 2 Paragraph 1 Letter a PA proves to be inadequate, in order to achieve sufficient climate protection, the obligation under Article 20a of the German Constitution to seek a solution to the climate protection problem at the international level is also updated; in particular, attempts should be made to achieve stricter agreements..." (own translation of Bundesverfassungsgericht (2021)).

i.e. around 1.5 °C above pre-industrial levels, applies. These politically determined goals do not correspond to what scientists (now) consider necessary. As Abbott et al. (2023, 1) write: “Despite convincing evidence that 1.5°C of warming would cause immense disruption to Earth systems, especially human civilization, many policymakers and researchers continue to treat this target as acceptable, or at least as the best future that remains attainable. If sustained through the end of the century or longer, this level of warming would very likely result in immense damage to human society, pervasive decline of life on Earth, and transformation of Earth's physical structure”

If the world stays on its current path, the global average temperature is expected to rise by 2.1–3.9 °C by 2100 (Liu et al., 2021). The latest IPCC report, the Synthesis Report 2023, describes the effects on sea level height as follows: “At sustained warming levels between 2 °C and 3 °C, the Greenland and West Antarctic ice sheets will be lost almost completely and irreversibly over multiple millennia, causing several metres of sea level rise (...) Due to deep uncertainty linked to ice-sheet processes, global mean sea level rise above the likely range – approaching 2 m by 2100 and in excess of 15 m by 2300 under the very high GHG emissions scenario (SSP5-8.5) (low confidence) – cannot be excluded.” (IPCC, 2023, 19). In the further course, a final sea level rise of more than 40 m cannot be ruled out, namely if an increase of 6–9 °C results in the East Antarctic ice sheet largely melting (Garbe et al., 2020).

The still relatively new research on existential risks to humanity emphasizes the cumulative effects of individual risks. Individual climate-related risks – extreme weather events, malnutrition and starvation due to crop failures, armed conflicts and vector-borne diseases – will each cause major to catastrophic damage. In combination, these individual risks could become an existential, uncontrollable multi-crisis and lead to the collapse of state systems (Kemp et al., 2022). Rising sea levels, for example, will lead to dramatic land loss. According to United Nations estimates, around 2.8 billion people now live within a maximum distance of 100 km from the coast. Of the world's twenty megacities, each with more than 10 million people, thirteen are located near the coast. These include the cities of Mumbai (18.2 million), Dhaka (14.4 million), Istanbul (14.4 million), Kolkata (14.3 million) and Beijing (14.3 million) (World Ocean Review, 2017). But cities in the global north such as New York (8.4 million), Osaka (2.6 million), Hamburg (1.8 million) and Bremen (570 000) would also have to be abandoned. Fig. 5 shows the coastline of the North Sea as it could develop with a global sea level rise of around 7 m, corresponding to the extensive melting of the Greenland ice sheet (Ward, 2010, 13). The mouth of the Elbe would then have become a branch of the North Sea and would divide Hamburg in two, while Bremerhaven will be completely flooded, and Bremen will be largely flooded.

We must avoid such scenarios at all costs. It follows that we must massively increase our efforts to avoid greenhouse gas emissions. And we need to look for ways to quickly bring concentrations back into the safe range below 350 ppm.

Fig. 5: The coastline of the North Sea with a sea level rise of approx. 7 m (flood.firetree.net, data from NASA, underlain map from OSM, openstreetmap.org)

This article is structured in such a way that a climate protection strategy is first presented that gives negative emissions more weight than before. The next step is to estimate the necessary extent of negative emissions. The removal procedures are then presented. Finally, the question of storing amounts of gaseous CO₂ or carbon after CO₂ capture at point sources is discussed. The article works with global data but is primarily aimed at actors in German-speaking countries.

2.A new dual strategy for the global community: CO₂ avoidance and CO₂ removal

2.1 The role of negative emissions in the future climate protection strategy

The IPCC has been consistently pointing out the importance of negative emissions for years in its report sections on CO₂ extraction and storage:

“All pathways that limit global warming to 1.5 °C with limited or no overshoot project the use of carbon dioxide removal (CDR) on the order of 100 – 1000 Gt CO₂ over the 21st century. CDR would be used to compensate for residual emissions and, in most cases, achieve net negative emissions to return global warming to 1.5 °C following a peak.” (IPCC, 2018, 17; see also IPCC, 2021, WG III Ch. 6.4.2.5; see also IPCC, 2023, FN 47)

With a view to the CO₂ removals from the atmosphere required after 2050 in the German Climate Protection Act (Section 2), Fuss et al. (2021, 5) write: “Given that the broader innovation literature consistently notes that the development and deploy-

ment of new technologies takes long periods of time (several decades), the urgency of developing CO₂ capture technologies is largely unrecognized.” Edenhofer et al. (2023, 32) emphasize the urgency of addressing this option: “Scaling-up CDR is an urgent issue. Policy makers are tempted to perceive this option as a matter that should be dealt with only when deep and rapid emission reductions are already implemented. However, deployment at scale requires a consistent policy framework and credible incentive schemes as soon as possible.” The length of the journey from the laboratory through the pilot project to mass production and use cannot be underestimated.⁵ The approval processes for large-scale systems alone may take 10 years – and these can only begin once the system itself is fully developed.

Regarding the terminology: One could understand “carbon capture” as a general term for all types of “capture” of the gas CO₂, but it has become common practice to only understand it as the capture of new emissions at point sources.⁶ Carbon capture and sequestration (CCS) at fossil point sources can slow the further increase in atmospheric CO₂ concentrations but cannot reduce this concentration. The term “Carbon Dioxide Removal” (CDR) explicitly refers to negative CO₂ emissions that reduce the atmospheric CO₂ concentration. In this discussion contribution, a CCS approach within the framework of fossil business models is explicitly rejected. In this text we are concerned with CDR, i.e. negative CO₂ emissions. In the literature, the abbreviation CCS stands partly for “Carbon Capture and Sequestration” and partly for “Carbon Capture and Storage”. In this text we use the terms sequestration, and storage synonymously. What is always meant is the permanent storage of atmospheric CO₂ in other spheres of the Earth system, i.e. either in the biosphere or the geosphere. The reversal of the entire anthropogenic process that leads to CO₂ emission is also referred to in this paper with the neologism *remission*.

This article formulates a climate protection strategy that partially reverses the temperature rise of the last few decades. As mentioned, maintaining today's values of approx. 424 ppm or an approximately 1.2 °C temperature increase (as of 2023) is too risky. Avoidance (rapid massive reduction of all greenhouse gas emissions) and removal (large-scale removal and long-term sequestration of CO₂) are two branches of a strategy that complement each other: the more hydrocarbon deposits are not touched at all (“Leave it in the ground”), the less CO₂ humanity has to remove from the atmosphere. Avoidance is a priority as long as there is not enough renewable energy available for extraction. In the meantime, the necessary conditions should be created so that extraction in the gigaton range can begin as soon as possible.

In addition to operating the CO₂ removal infrastructure, its construction also requires energy. The higher the proportion of renewable energies used, the lower the associated emissions, which of course also have to be taken into account in the greenhouse gas budget.

⁵ Steam engines took 300 years to go from the original 0.1% efficiency to today's 45%.

⁶ Point sources are all easily accessible CO₂ streams in which the gas is present in high concentration and as a large mass flow, making it worthwhile to install a capture system there.

Fig. 6: Scenario of an immediate and drastic reduction in CO₂ emissions. Note: For simplified presentation, conventional onshore CDR is not taken into account. Own figure, after Erlach et al. (2022, 3).

Fig. 6 illustrates the scenario of an immediate and drastic reduction in CO₂ emissions. In this scenario, the need for necessary CO₂ extraction is reduced to a minimum.

Such a scenario is illusory because, although there are still some “low-hanging fruits” when it comes to avoidance (Linow et al., 2022), on a global scale many factors can hardly be influenced and will continue to contribute to the increase in CO₂ concentrations in the near future. To truly implement the scenario shown in Fig. 6, it would require an extremely focused global effort, in which many habits, demands, access to resources, distribution of wealth, etc. would have to be completely reorganized within a few years. This scenario is technically possible, but socially and on a global scale it does not seem realistic.

Explanation box 2: An example of established behavioral patterns is meat consumption, which continues to increase worldwide. Throughout the 300,000-year history of the species *homo sapiens*, it has not been a moral question of whether one should eat meat, but rather one of survival. It has only recently become a question of individual moral consideration. Therefore, one cannot expect that there will be radical behavioral changes on a global scale in the shortest possible time.

In a realistic scenario (see Fig. 7), CO₂ emissions will be reduced more slowly than in Fig. 6, although this scenario is still extremely ambitious compared to current forecasts. At the same time, large-scale CO₂ removal will begin as quickly as possible. To estimate the necessary negative emissions, global CO₂ emissions of currently almost 40 Gt/year, of which around 0.76 Gt are in Germany, must be used.

Another comparative figure is that a reduction in the CO₂ concentration of 1 ppm in the atmosphere today corresponds to 7.8 Gt (excluding oceanic uptake of CO₂). A large proportion of the carbon dioxide emitted from fossil fuels is now in the oceans because air and seawater are in close contact. This carbon dioxide must be extracted using CDR in addition to that present in the air. Just as emissions do not lead one to

one to an increase in atmospheric CO₂, negative emissions will not lead one to one to a decrease in concentration. If you divide around 2400 Gt of CO₂ emissions since pre-industrial times (IPCC, 2021, SPM Table 2) by an increase of around 140 ppm since pre-industrial times, the result is an estimate of somewhat more than 17 Gt of CO₂ per ppm increase. A reduction to 350 ppm (and thus a reduction in global warming to approx. 1 °C) corresponds to an extraction of approx. 1250 Gt CO₂. If we also take into account around 500 Gt of CO₂ emissions in the period from 2022 to 2100 (78 years), the negative emissions required are an extraction of around 1750 Gt of CO₂ by the year 2100.⁷ If we take into account that the extraction must first increase, in order to then reach a constant level, around 40 Gt per year of negative emissions will be necessary.

For Germany, the share of unavoidable residual emissions was calculated at 0.063 Gt CO₂/year (Prognos 2021).⁸

Fig. 7: Schematic representation of the dual strategy of avoiding emissions and removing carbon dioxide from the atmosphere. Land use effects are not taken into account. Source: ars.els-cdn.com/content/image/1-s2.0-S0360544223005935-gr11.jpg, from Keiner et al. (2023), CC BY 4.0).

⁷ Using a slightly different calculation approach, Keiner et al (2023) also determined the extraction of 1750 Gt. Other estimates expect higher residual emissions (Buck et al., 2023).

⁸ The KSpG evaluation report (Bundesregierung, 2022, 122-126, 133-134) examined various studies on how Germany could become greenhouse gas neutral. All of the six scenarios examined in this context require the use of CO₂ capture in different quantities in order to achieve greenhouse gas neutrality. The required use of CCS by 2045 reaches a volume of 0.034 Gt CO₂/a in the *dena* lead study and up to 0.073 Mt CO₂/a in the Agora energy transition study, so it varies considerably.

This dual strategy of avoiding emissions and removing carbon dioxide from the atmosphere should be backed up with intermediate goals in terms of both the red curve (decreasing gross emissions) and the green curve (negative emissions), such as achieving net zero in the decade 2040 – 2050. Avoiding all CO₂ emissions is the essential first step towards a 1.0° C target (Breyer et al., 2022).⁹

The long-term goal of negative carbon dioxide emissions is not only to compensate for further emissions of all relevant greenhouse gases (this would lead to greenhouse gas neutrality), but also to overcompensate in order to achieve climate neutrality.¹⁰ The excess of negative emissions will lead to a gradual decrease in atmospheric CO₂ concentration and the Earth's surface temperature will begin to fall. Once the desired climate has been restored, a CO₂ flow equilibrium – i. e. the same level of output and input (emissions and extraction) – will have to become humanity's model for the next few centuries.

2.2. The false narrative about the remaining budget

Assuming humanity has a “remaining emissions budget” implies ignoring the dangers of an irreversible course towards “*Hothouse Earth*” (Steffen et al., 2018). If you take 350 ppm (corresponding to approximately 1 °C warming) as the target, then there is no remaining budget, on the contrary: we have already significantly exceeded our budget. But even if you consider 1.5 °C warming to be acceptable, humanity no longer has any remaining budget. The IPCC currently sees a small remaining budget for a few years: “If the annual CO₂ emissions between 2020 and 2030 stayed, on average, at the same level as 2019, the resulting cumulative emissions would almost exhaust the remaining carbon budget for 1.5 °C (50%) and deplete more than a third of the re-

⁹ For other greenhouse gases, their different residence times in the atmosphere must also be taken into account, e. g. for methane (CH₄), the concentration falls to 1/e, i.e. to 37%, after 12 years (Umweltbundesamt, 2020). However, methane's potential to contribute to global warming is 80 times greater than that of CO₂ on a 20-year time scale. The release of methane results from wet meadows, extraction of fossil raw materials, rice cultivation, animal husbandry, etc. The very different sources make it difficult to control them. With methane, due to its short residence time, it would be sufficient to keep emissions stable at the level of the year 2000 in order to keep the concentration in the atmosphere and the methane greenhouse effect constant. Other (technical) greenhouse gases, on the other hand, sometimes remain in the atmosphere for an extremely long time and at the same time have an extremely high greenhouse effect (SF₆, CF₄, C₂F₆, etc.). This greenhouse effect can only be compensated for by converting it into CO₂ equivalents and then reducing the CO₂ concentration. A more detailed treatment can be found, for example, in CarbonBrief (2021). In addition, the effect that with a reduction in CO₂ emissions the cooling effect of aerosols also decreases is also discussed there. This would therefore have to be compensated for by additional negative emissions.

¹⁰ In the glossary of the KSpG evaluation, both terms are differentiated as follows:

“*Climate neutrality*: A stage or a process in which human activities have no net effect on the climate system. In addition to the greenhouse gas balance, climate neutrality also takes into account other effects of human activities, such as aerosols in the atmosphere or changes in the Earth's albedo (Deutsche Energie-Agentur, 2020).”

“*Greenhouse gas neutrality*: The balance between anthropogenic emissions of greenhouse gases and the removal of such gases through negative emissions (CDR) (KSG § 2 Para. 9). In addition to CO₂, greenhouse gas neutrality also takes into account other greenhouse gases, namely methane (CH₄), nitrous oxide (N₂O), and various F-gases. A synonym for this is *net zero*.”

maintaining carbon budget for 2 °C (67%).” (IPCC 2023, 20)¹¹. But this is based on a probability of occurrence that we consider unacceptable. No rational individual would undertake an avoidable journey if the probability of arriving alive was only 50% or 67%. In Assessment Report 6, the IPCC itself questioned the risk ethics premises made in previous assessment reports: “Previous IPCC reports largely focused their assessment on the projected *very likely* range of future surface warming and associated climate change. However, a comprehensive risk assessment also requires considering the potentially larger changes in the physical climate system that are *unlikely* or *very unlikely* but possible and potentially associated with the highest risks for society and ecosystems (Figure TS.6). Since AR5, the development of physical climate storylines of high warming has emerged as a useful approach for exploring the future risk space that lies outside of the IPCC *very likely* range projections.” (IPCC, 2021, Box TS.3). The cited IPCC partial report shows that 300 Gt CO₂ is still available as a budget for 83% target achievement of 1.5 °C from 2020, of which 220 Gt CO₂ should be taken into account as a margin of error in order to ensure a sufficiently large safety margin to comply with the critical temperature limits. If the precautionary principle described above is taken seriously, these 220 Gt of CO₂ must be deducted. According to this calculation, the remaining 80 Gt of CO₂, with humanity's annual emissions of just under 40 Gt of CO₂, will have been used up in the second quarter of 2022. This also speaks in favour of making a paradigm shift and abandoning the remaining budget narrative.

3. The role of companies and private individuals in the new dual strategy: Ethical considerations

3.1 Negative emissions in climate ethics

Over the last thirty years, debates in non-natural scientific disciplines (e. g. ethics and economics) at the international level have focused on mitigation, adaptation and loss and damage caused by climate change. With the restoration of previous climate conditions (climate repair/climate restoration), a fourth field of discourse has recently been added that addresses the question of who has to remove how much CO₂ from the atmosphere and when.

From an economic perspective, for example, the question arises as to how CDR should be reflected in European emissions trading. In just over two decades, the last emissions permit under the European Emissions Trading System (EU-ETS) will be sold. The remaining emissions must be offset by permits generated through CDR options (Edenhofer et al., 2023, 32).

¹¹ The stated probabilities for meeting these limits result from ensembles of climate models in which parameters were varied within their uncertainties.

From an ethical point of view, the principle of shared but differentiated responsibility applies to the extraction strategy – just as to the avoidance strategy. The question of who causes pollution plays a major role, because it stands to reason that the extent of one's own climate pollution should be a target for the extent of one's own CO₂ removal. In addition to government emitters (example statements: Germany produces around 2% of global greenhouse gas emissions; China produces around 33% of global greenhouse gas emissions, etc.), numerous new articles focus on the emissions of certain income groups or classes (e. g. Bruckner et al., 2022; Cass et al., 2023; Chancel, 2022). The latest IPCC report also contains a statement on this: “The 10% of households with the highest per capita emissions contribute 34 – 45% of global consumption-based household GHG emissions, while the bottom 50% contribute 13 – 15%.” (IPCC, 2023, 8).

Until recently, it was not possible for individual companies or private individuals to reduce their individual CO₂ footprint or bring it to zero by removing CO₂. That has changed, and new debates have also developed in ethics (cf. Moss & Umbers 2020). Ethicist Hanna Schübel (2022) argued “that the possibility of removing emissions from the atmosphere brings with it the moral responsibility to minimize the individual carbon dioxide footprint to zero. In order not to cause any damage through emissions, the individual can not only avoid their production, but also ensure that they are removed from the atmosphere.” Building on this, Tremmel (2023) argues that the existential threat posed by climate change creates the corporate and individual responsibility to reduce the carbon footprint to net zero, even if others do not act in the same way. This last point, the obligation to act even if others do not comply, is not without controversy in climate ethics (see for pros and cons: Broome, 2019; Budolfson et al., 2021; Cripps, 2013; Gesang, 2017; Hedberg, 2018; Hourdequin, 2010; Johnson, 2003; Maheshwari, 2022; Morgan-Knapp & Goodman, 2015; Nefsky, 2021; Nolt, 2013; Sandler, 2010; Schwenkenbecher, 2014, Sinnott-Armstrong, 2005; Song, 2017) and depends, among other things, on whether one is of the empirical (i.e. non-normative) view that the tipping points have already been reached or are exceeded. However, if one is of the opinion that it is still possible for humanity to prevent runaway climate change (i.e. an ever-worsening development with rising temperatures, floods, droughts, etc.), then the following applies:

- 1) Let's assume that ten people could, without endangering themselves, prevent an event in which ten other people would die over the next eighty years. Would they then have a duty or responsibility to prevent this event?
- 2) Let's assume that thousand people could, without endangering themselves, prevent an event in which thousand other people would die over the next eighty years. Would they then have a duty or responsibility to prevent this event?
- 3) Let's assume that one million people could, without endangering themselves, prevent an event in which one million other people would die over the next eighty years. Would this group of people then have a duty or responsibility to prevent this event?

From an ethical perspective, the answer to the last question is yes, just like the questions before it. With the increasing number of actors, individual responsibility does not disappear (Tremmel, 2023).

Only when something is empirically possible does the question arise in ethics as to whether one should do it. Should implies can. For several years now, companies and private individuals have had the opportunity to reduce their personal CO₂ footprint to zero through a change in lifestyle, combined with financing negative emissions (see Bilharz, 2021). When purchasing certificates, individuals can choose between biological and geological CO₂ remission projects.¹² Climate ethics is therefore faced with the challenge of incorporating this fact into its ethical considerations. From an ethical perspective, “do no harm” and “clean up your own mess” are two complementary principles, as climate ethicist Henry Shue (2017, 593) points out: “Strikingly, 'do no harm' and 'clean up your own mess' are the two sides of the same coin: those who fail to fulfil the first responsibility ordinarily incur the second responsibility. If one does contribute to harm, in violation of the negative responsibility, it becomes one’s positive responsibility to correct it—and perhaps compensate for it as well.” If you translate Shue's expression “mess” with the change of the earth's climate by humans, and if you develop his thoughts further, the relationship between the two ethical principles “do no harm” and “clean up your own mess” can be represented as in Fig. 8.

Fig. 8: Ethical decision tree for non-state actors. © Jörg Tremmel

It is often not the will that is lacking among wealthy players, but rather the lack of information about the new certificates. However, a label fraud is also responsible for this. To date, there has not been a sufficient conceptual distinction between compensation certificates and remission certificates. Only the latter really lead to CO₂ extraction and storage, i.e. to negative emissions. In the area of holiday flights, for example, the company *atmosfair* offers compensation certificates with which emissions are avoided elsewhere in the world, while *Climeworks* offers emission certificates with which atmospheric CO₂ is brought back into the earth's crust. In the area of certificates for companies, the largest companies in the world have in the past been certified as CO₂ neutral by agencies such as Verra. The CO₂ emissions of these companies continue unabated. “Companies can pay for a climate protection project somewhere in the world to reduce the emissions they emit by extracting gas, building cars, manufacturing computers. On paper, this is a win-win deal. Because the atmosphere doesn't care whether emissions decrease on the Volkswagen factory premises or in a forest in Zimbabwe. The main thing is that they go back. Someone just has to guarantee that

¹² The company *Climeworks* offers certificates for storage in basalt rock, and the *char2cool* association offers certificates for biochar.

the CO₂ is actually saved.” (Fischer & Knuth, 2023). Numerous abuses have recently been uncovered in this compensation market because, in fact, much less CO₂ was saved than the certificates promised (Fischer & Knuth, 2023; Vorrath, 2023). But the problem lies deeper: compensation certificates are directly linked to the narrative of the remaining CO₂ budget for humanity, which, as shown above, is false. They led to more and more companies describing themselves and their business model as CO₂-neutral – while at the same time the CO₂ concentration in the atmosphere is rising ever faster. In relation to Fig. 8, it would be like saying: “I don't clean up after myself, but I make sure that my neighbour doesn't make a mess.” The problem with this is that at least one pile of dirt remains in any case.

3.2. Who is paying?

The obligation to achieve net zero (instead of gross zero) postulated here could be countered by the argument that many actors would be financially overwhelmed. In any case, such financial overtaxing does not exist for high-earning companies and for the many millions of individuals worldwide who have an annual income of more than € 100 000 and sufficient assets. But couldn't the non-state actors simply continue with their current climate-damaging lifestyle and then “wash their names” with return certificates? This argument is flawed, as empirical evidence shows. In order not to have to buy certificates in large quantities, a climate-conscious, moral, but also economically minded company or individual considers avoiding emissions from the start. When weighing up the two options a) avoidance and b) extraction, companies and individuals who previously did neither a) nor b) also begin to avoid emissions. This shows that for individuals and corporations (unlike states), there is usually no competition between funds for prevention and funds for extraction. A pioneer was Microsoft (Joppa et al., 2021), as this company has set itself the goal of achieving net zero in current emissions by 2030 – and of having eliminated all previous emissions since the company was founded in 1975 by 2050.¹³ This strategy automatically led (and continues to lead) to increased avoidance efforts. It is no different for private individuals who have set a goal of net zero. Anyone who has previously emitted a lot of CO₂

¹³ Ethically speaking, it would be overly demanding to demand that all companies now or in the future offset all emissions that have arisen since their founding. For some companies, the founding date was many decades ago, so the costs would be exorbitant. From an ethical perspective, morally reprehensible actions also depend on knowledge (ability). At the time of the Industrial Revolution, climate science did not yet exist, and the climate-warming effects of carbon dioxide and other gases were unknown. Gradually the essential connections of anthropogenic climate change were explored. In the first IPCC report in 1990, the majority of the reviewed articles evaluated supported the hypothesis that current climate change is man-made; numerous scientific papers had already postulated the connection. The thesis was solidified in the second IPCC report in 1995 and is no longer seriously doubted today. Most climate ethicists see either the publication of the first IPCC report in 1990 (Tremmel & Robinson, 2014) or the second IPCC report (Meyer, 2022) as the point at which the ignorance argument no longer applies. You can therefore prima facie make a moral demand on an extremely well-earning company like Microsoft to offset all of the company's own emissions since 1990. For the period between 1975 (when the company was founded) and 1990, this would be desirable, but not morally required behaviour on the part of Microsoft. For the complex and ramified discussion about “historical emissions,” which cannot be included in this article due to space limitations (see Meyer, 2011; Meyer & Roser 2013; Meyer & Sanklecha, 2017; Pozo et al., 2020; Tremmel, 2013; Tremmel & Robinson 2014, 117-132).

into the air through flights now realizes how expensive it is to have the corresponding amount of CO₂ removed afterwards by purchasing reliable remission certificates. So the flights are at least partially avoided from the start.

It has important implications for the financial viability of the new dual strategy if climate ethics postulates the moral obligation for companies and natural persons to reduce their own climate footprint to net zero, if this is possible without excessive financial demands. Numerous non-state actors would be persuaded to reallocate funds to climate protection. In this scenario, through these new financial resources raised by non-state actors alone, so many direct air capture systems (DAC systems) could be built in a short time that this technology could be used to remove gigatons of CO₂ from the atmosphere every year. The upscaling of DAC systems has so far failed due to financial, not technical, restrictions. This is a technology that has been known since the 1960s and has been used in niche areas ever since, although many processes still need to be optimized.

As far as the state as a financier is concerned, there is a serious objection: critics of a greater emphasis on Negative Emissions Technologies (NET) argue that the billions that the state would spend on this would not be used to promote emissions avoidance (wind farms, solar systems, heat pumps, etc.). However, the dilemma can be resolved by explicitly setting separate goals for avoidance and removal (Erlach et al., 2022: 4). For Germany, it is not clear how or why the current CO₂ reduction targets could be affected by an ambitious strategy for negative emissions. The Climate Protection Act prescribes binding annual savings targets up to the desired greenhouse gas neutrality in 2045, with the interim targets being a reduction of 88% by 2040 and 65% by 2030 (always compared to the reference year 1990). What has not happened yet (but is urgently needed) is the federal government setting a specific annual target value for negative emissions. States should therefore set two values for the next decades. The higher value will be that for CO₂ avoidance, at least until 2050, i.e. the focus of the dual strategy described here is on CO₂ avoidance (Altermatt et al., 2023; Clausen et al., 2022; Gerhards et al., 2021). But well before 2050, countries must launch negative emissions technologies at least through basic research and changing the legal framework, otherwise these technologies will not be available in 2050. An example of urgently needed regulation: In order to establish a quality seal for various CDR measures, an agency should be set up at EU level to evaluate the certificates and, if necessary, approve them for the market.¹⁴ The EU Commission has already presented a first draft for this, but from the perspective of the EU Parliament it still needs to be improved.¹⁵

¹⁴ “A Carbon Removal Certification Authority (CRCA) should be established to carry out independent certification based on scientific assessments of all relevant CDR technologies and in particular their properties with respect to permanence and additionality. This also includes setting up procedures for calculating and verifying discount factors due to impermanence and imperfect additionality. Because of ongoing technological and economic progress as well as emerging scientific insights, certification rules and discount factors should be updated regularly” (Edenhofer et al., 2023, 30).

¹⁵ For the status of this debate, which cannot be deepened here, see European Parliament (2024).

As a method for negative emissions in the context of these climate goals, in the next section we will focus on two important approaches to reducing CO₂ concentrations in the atmosphere. First of all, “CO₂-to-stone”, i.e. the mineralization of CO₂ after chemical reactions with rocks in the Earth’s crust, is addressed. A section on the capture at point sources and the storage of the gas CO₂ in the geological subsurface follows.

4. Processes for reducing the CO₂ concentration in the atmosphere

The capture (and storage) of CO₂ in industrial production processes (e. g. cement industry) can reduce the further increase in the concentration of CO₂ in the atmosphere but cannot reduce this concentration. Since the focus of this article is on CDR (instead of CCS), methods for reducing the CO₂ concentration in the atmosphere will first be discussed below. Today's value of approximately 424 ppm is already too high, as explained in Chapter 1. Two ways to remove the CO₂ already present in the atmosphere, presented in detail here, are the techniques Direct Air Carbon Capture and Sequestration (DACCS) and Bioenergy Carbon Capture and Sequestration (BECCS).¹⁶

4.1. DACCS

With DACCS, CO₂ is removed directly from the ambient air. This requires processes to efficiently separate CO₂ from other molecules in the air (nitrogen, water, etc.). The costs for this are estimated at 60–340 US \$/t (Baylin-Stern & Berghout, 2021; Breyer et al., 2019; Fasihi et al., 2019; Keith et al., 2018; see also the range of 100–300 US \$/t in Table 1). The difference in the forecasts is explained, among other things, by the fact that the DACCS costs are heavily dependent on the energy price, about whose further development there are very different views. At the World Economic Forum 2023, reducing the cost or price of DACCS was identified as a central task.¹⁷ As mentioned, the company *Climeworks* currently offers certificates for companies and private individuals, covering both direct air capture and subsequent storage (in the form of mineralization). However, the *Climeworks* certificate for the remission of one ton of CO₂ costs € 900–1000. Several other companies are currently preparing the second wave of DAC as start-ups. In the next few years, these companies will join the market for remission certificates and then offer the services documented in the certificates at cheaper prices.¹⁸ Through more efficient separation methods (Sandru et al., 2022)

¹⁶ Concerning further methods, Fuhrman et al. (2023), Fuss et al. (2021), Linow et al. (2022) and Smith et al. (2023) provide a good overview. See also Deutsches Klima-Konsortium (2017, Fig. 1).

¹⁷ The management consultancy BCG also considers this to be feasible, see World Economic Forum (2023).

¹⁸ 120 providers of certificates for negative emissions are tracked on the CDR website (<https://www.cdr.fyi/>) (as of October 5, 2023). Tree plantings are explicitly excluded from this because the amounts of CO₂ removed are generally considered unmeasurable or too uncertain. Specific measures in the areas of, for example, bio-

and scaling of the systems, costs could be reduced year after year. For example, *Carbon Capture Inc.'s Project Bison* has set a goal of filtering five megatons of CO₂ (0.005 Gt) from the air annually starting in 2030.¹⁹

There are different DAC technologies, but in all of them the goal of separating carbon from the ambient air is achieved through two different phases (Shayegh et al., 2021, 2): Air containing carbon dioxide is passed into a washing liquid (*absorbent*). Since amines bind carbon dioxide very selectively, an amine solution is almost always used as the washing liquid, whereby the binding of CO₂ to the amine (*absorption*) is reversible.²⁰ If the amine is saturated with CO₂, this compound is heated in a second step to approx. 100–120 °C (Fasihi et al., 2019) in order to separate the bound CO₂ from the amine again (regeneration process). The captured CO₂ is now in pure and highly concentrated form and is mixed with water in the next step. This “sparkling water” is then pressed underground. The light carbonic acid dissolves basalt rock, with the CO₂ turning into bicarbonate (Vorrath, 2023; see also Fig. 9 right) before it mineralizes.

Table 1: Different CDR methods in comparison. Global potential of relevant CDR technologies, in Gt CO₂/year (estimate for 2050), and costs, in US\$/t CO₂ based on today's purchasing power. Storage times for various CO₂ removal technologies are indicated by half-life. Adapted from Edenhofer et al. (2023); based on Hepburn et al. (2019); Hiriashi et al. (2014); Lehmann et al. (2021); Smith et al. (2006); Smith et al. (2023); Woolf et al. (2021).

Technology	Potential in Gt CO ₂ /year	Costs in US\$/t CO ₂	Duration of storage
DACCS	5–40	100–300	Millennia
BECCS	0.5–11	100–200	Millennia
Biochar	0.3–6,6	30–120	Centuries
Changes in land use	2–5	0–100	Years to decades
(Re)forestation	0.5–10	0–50	Decades to centuries
Enhanced weathering	2–4	50–200	Centuries
Ocean alkalization	1–100	14–500	Centuries

char, enhanced weathering and mineralization are shown. In total, certificates for 5 Mt of CO₂ have already been sold, but only three percent of them have been implemented. The people and companies who buy these certificates are essentially crowdfunding a new clean tech industry in the making.

¹⁹ See Carbon Capture (n.d.) However, there appear to be delays in the schedule (Hiar, 2023).

²⁰ However, the amine solution degrades over time. Since the regeneration process in particular is very energy-intensive, methods are being tested in order to reduce costs (Sandru et al., 2022).

The quantities injected so far, e.g. the *CarbFix* project in Iceland (0.000004 Gt CO₂/year for *Carbfix1* or 0.000012 Gt CO₂/year for *Carbfix2*), are still small, but allow initial conclusions to be drawn. After two years, *Carbfix1* was able to demonstrate that 90 % of the injected CO₂ had combined with the calcium, magnesium and iron contained in the basalt to form solid carbonate (at a depth of 500 m and water temperatures approximately 30 °C). At *CarbFix2*, at a depth of 800 m and a temperature of around 250 °C, it was 80 % within less than 3 months. The process requires around 25 t of water per t of CO₂, at 25 °C and 25 bar. The amount of water required is therefore large, although the water can be recycled and used in closed-loop operation. This process, developed for basalt, could also be used for other rocks. The costs for storage using the *CarbFix1* method were estimated from 30 €/t (at 57 000 t/year) to 12.5 €/t (at 400 000 t/year) (excluding the costs of direct air capture).²¹ Storing carbonate in solid form has the advantage of very high security and permanence. The amount of CO₂ that is locked away can be easily calculated – unlike, for example, with tree planting. From this point of view, CO₂-to-stone is the best method for negative emissions.

With DAC, however, the energy consumption is high at around 950–3 000 kWh/t CO₂ (Fasihi et al., 2019; Keith et al., 2018; Ma, 2022; National Academy of Sciences, Engineering and Medicine, 2018), which is why the process is only useful when using renewable energies. The use of fossil fuels is out of the question for this process because then CO₂ would be emitted to remove CO₂. The proportion of CO₂ in the ambient air is (virtually) the same everywhere, regardless of whether it is the air over Iceland, Oman or Berlin. However, only places where green energies such as geothermal energy, solar energy or hydropower²² are available in abundance and at the same time the suitable storage rocks are available are suitable for DAC systems. Iceland – a gigantic basalt block (Vorrath, 2023) – is suitable, but basalt formations (ophiolites) are also currently being intensively investigated in Oman. All places where a) rock that reacts with carbonic acid and b) local energy supplies with 100% renewable energies are available are suitable for the CO₂-to-stone process.²³ All previous estimates for storage capacities are promising. Snæbjörnsdóttir et al. (2020) estimate that 100 000–250 000 Gt of CO₂ could be stored through the formation of carbonates in reactive rocks within a time frame of a few years. This estimate is based on experience, for example from geothermal systems, which suggest a storage capacity of up to 125 kg CO₂/m³ in basalt up to 500 m depth (Oelkers et al., 2023; Wiese et al., 2008). With their more conservative estimate of 10 kg CO₂/m³, Oelkers et al. (2023) estimate the storage capacity of individual basalt provinces and peridotite massifs, summing up the global total capacity to 34 000–42 000 Gt CO₂. This is also a multiple of the amount of 1750 Gt of CO₂ that humanity should remove from the atmosphere.

²¹ Costs for other methods are listed by Oelkers et al. (2023).

²² When it comes to hydropower, trade-offs with other goals such as landscape preservation must be taken into account.

²³ ElSayed et al. (2023) use Egypt as an example to show that DACCS could easily be integrated into an exclusively renewable energy system.

Fig. 9. Left: Direct Air Capture (DAC) facility in Iceland. Source: <https://climeworks.com/>. Right: Basalt with carbonate minerals in which the CO₂ that was previously in the atmosphere is bound (both © Climeworks, right of use granted).

The DAC system shown in Fig. 9 ("Orca" from *Climeworks*) occupies around half a hectare and filters around 4000 t of CO₂ from the air every year.

As far as DACCS is concerned, scaling it up to the necessary scale over the next few decades is an ambitious but not utopian goal. *Climeworks* is currently building its second facility (*Mammoth*) on Iceland. From 2024, it should be able to remove around 36 000 t (0.000036 Gt) of CO₂ from the air per year. After the second system, the third will come, which in turn will accomplish five to ten times the amount, etc. The financial investments that have been made in DAC systems worldwide since the beginning of this decade can, with little uncertainty, be converted into concrete withdrawal quantities in the next years. In the US, the Inflation Reduction Act and the Bipartisan Infrastructure Act together provide billions of dollars to support the development and deployment of approaches to extracting CO₂ from the atmosphere, including US \$3.5 billion for four DAC hubs alone (Williams 2023).

The problem remains that the price is currently very high: a survey of eighteen experts considers a price reduction to US \$200/t CO₂ by 2050 to be the most likely price scenario under otherwise current economic and ecological conditions (Shayegh et al., 2021, 1). But neither the increases in extraction quantities nor the reductions in the costs per ton of CO₂ will occur on their own: Favourable conditions for investments and a positive attitude of the population towards this technology are prerequisites.

4.2. BECCS

With BECCS, biomass is burned to generate energy and the resulting carbon dioxide is captured. Koornneef et al. (2012) estimate that up to 10.4 Gt CO₂/year can be removed from the atmosphere by 2050 (see also Table 1, where the range is given as 0.5 – 11 Gt). However, to implement BECCS on this scale, large areas of land are required to cultivate biomass. In principle, this means that there is competition for land with land for food production and biosphere protection. Global food security could

therefore be significantly jeopardized by BECCS (Fujimori et al., 2022) and could also further reduce an already decreased biodiversity (Hanssen et al., 2022). Günther & Ekardt (2022) point out that large-scale use of BECCS can also lead to significant human rights violations.

The required area can be reduced by using plants that remove as much CO₂ as possible per area. Mashoreng et al. (2019) estimate that the carbon binding capacity of cultivated algae in the sea is around 5 800 t/km²/year, i.e. an area of around 1.7 million km² would be required for 10 Gt CO₂/year (for comparison, the total cultivated land area worldwide is around 47 million km²). Water hyacinths would be even more effective in carbon capture – around 30 000 t dry matter per km² per year, corresponding to around 90 000 t CO₂/km²/year (Danner, 2021).

4.3. Other methods

Currently, about 2 Gt of CO₂/year is removed from the atmosphere by modifying land surface to absorb atmospheric CO₂ using conventional means – for example by planting trees, restoring damaged forests and rewetting peatlands, or enriching the soil. New methods such as BECCS and Biochar (biochar) so far only account for around 0.002 Gt CO₂/year, i.e. a thousandth of that (Naddaf 2023; Smith et al. 2023). In contrast, there are also 4 Gt CO₂/year emissions from changes in land use (Global Carbon Project, 2021). For comparison: currently an amount of 11 Gt CO₂/year is net absorbed in the biosphere through natural processes (Global Carbon Project, 2021)²⁴. However, the theoretical potential is much larger, especially since around 440 Gt of CO₂ is absorbed into the biosphere and released again every year. However, a more detailed treatment of this topic is beyond the scope of this paper.

The above-mentioned methods for removing CO₂ from the atmosphere with near-surface storage of the carbon in organic form are the rewetting of peatlands, large-scale afforestation, which can be achieved, for example, through desalination-based irrigation (Caldera & Breyer, 2023) or pyrogenic carbon capture and sequestration (PyCCS). These procedures are often comparatively inexpensive, but less long-term and sometimes imply a higher risk that the carbon will escape again (see Table 1). Weizsäcker (2022, 47 f.) discusses further disadvantages of some “nature-based solutions”. It happened that land was taken away from indigenous peoples through legally problematic steps in order to plant trees there, which also did not belong there climatically and biologically. However, if used correctly, reforestation can also have positive side effects and should therefore be included (Yuwono et al. 2023). For further discussion of *nature-based solutions* see also Linow et al. (2022).

The long-term geological storage of carbon dioxide through (artificially significantly increased) weathering of volcanic rock requires significantly less energy compared to

²⁴ However, this natural sink does not relieve us of the need to remove additional CO₂ from the atmosphere, since the natural uptake of CO₂ in the oceans and the biosphere only approximately compensates for the increase in temperature that would occur at constant concentrations because the system is not in thermal equilibrium (see, e. g., CarbonBrief, 2021). Additionally, this may be a temporary effect due to the higher concentration of CO₂ in the atmosphere.

DACCS: suitable rock is ground into small pieces and then spread over a large area on suitable areas. This method is particularly useful if it is used at the same time to improve soil properties in agriculture. Germany has large deposits of well-suited rock, particularly in the Eifel and Vogelsberg (Borchers et al., 2022). In a similar way, ocean alkalization increases the buffering capacity of the ocean, and the associated CO₂ uptake is expected to be persistent on time scales of millennia (Hartmann et al., 2023).²⁵

4.4. Comparison between geological and biological methods

Chiquier et al. (2022) and Joppa et al. (2021) compare the efficiency and the elapsed time between use and removal, and the durability for different methods of CO₂ removal. Fig. 10 and Table 1 show potentials for CO₂ storage in the bio- and geosphere and their anticipated duration and costs.

Fig. 10: Comparison of duration, potential and costs of storage for various biological and geological methods, according to Table 1. For geological methods, however, the duration is likely to be much longer in many cases. The results of Kampman et al. (2016) show that in natural CO₂ reservoirs, no significant corrosion of the cap rock occurs even after 100 000 years. This is much longer than the 10 000 years needed to avoid an impact on the climate (University of Cambridge, 2016). (Own illustration.)

²⁵ For details on natural sinks in Germany, see the studies compared in the KSpG evaluation report, especially the 'Rescue Study' (Umweltbundesamt, 2019) and Borchers et al. (2022).

The geological methods remove the CO₂ (or, after its conversion, carbonate) from the atmosphere over geological time periods. Humanity is emitting geologically long-term CO₂ in the Anthropocene – so we should best let it disappear again in the same long-term.

Overall, the necessary negative emissions can most likely be achieved through a combination of different processes (Minx et al., 2018). Intermediate storage of CO₂ can also play a role, e. g. in construction timber. At the end of the useful life of around sixty years, the CO₂ can be geologically stored using technology that may have been improved by then. The fundamental ethical-economic questions of temporary storage, for example with regard to European emissions trading, cannot be addressed here (see Edenhofer, 2023; Fuss et al., 2021).

5. Deposition of CO₂ at point sources and geological storage as a gas in the pore space of sedimentary rocks

5.1 Methods of CO₂ capture at point sources

The following section deals with CO₂ emissions from point sources (e. g. cement production, chemical industry), which are often described as unavoidable.²⁶ In principle, CO₂ could also be separated from fossil power plants – but this would slow down the urgently needed structural change towards 100 % renewable energy. The effectiveness of CO₂ capture in power plants is around 90 %, i.e. 10 % of the CO₂ is still emitted into the atmosphere, and the significant air pollution from fossil power plants is even further increased because, due to the decreasing efficiency with CO₂ capture, more fossil fuel is needed. Air pollution makes the population sick – with correspondingly high costs for the health system (Galimova et al., 2022). In the area of energy production, the transition to renewables such as wind and sun is ultimately more cost-effective than ongoing fossil energy production with CCS (Diesing et al., 2023).²⁷ It is generally expected that fossil fuel companies will attempt to abuse negative emissions technologies as an extension strategy. This must be prevented by legal regulations (coal phase-out, etc.). Nevertheless, deposition at point sources should not be completely rejected as long as alternatives do not exist in practice for the emissions that, based on current knowledge, are unavoidable.

²⁶ According to Lopez et al. (2023) the chemical industry will be able to completely dispense with fossil raw materials in the future. In cement production, NORCEM from the Heidelberg Cement Group is planning the first CCS plant with the aim of no longer emitting CO₂ from 2030 (Gassnova, n.d.). Through recarbonatization - the binding of CO₂ in mineral building materials - the overall CO₂ balance of cement and calcareous building materials could even become negative (Bayerische Ingenieurkammer Bau, 2022).

²⁷ In Norway it is planned to produce “blue” hydrogen from natural gas and to store the resulting CO₂ using CCS. However, since blue hydrogen is produced from the vapor reduction of natural gas, the benefit to the climate is lower than when using green hydrogen, which only uses renewable energy sources for production, due to the high methane emissions during natural gas production and transport (Howarth & Jacobson, 2021).

Baylin-Stern & Berghout (2021) estimate the cost of CO₂ capture at point sources at 15 to 25 US \$/t CO₂ under today's economic and technical conditions and for industrial processes that generate pure or highly concentrated CO₂ streams (e. g. Ethanol production or natural gas processing). For processes with dilute gas streams, such as cement production and electricity generation, the costs under today's economic and technical conditions are 40 – 120 US \$/t CO₂. The energy required for the necessary compression for sequestration underground is in the order of 100 kWh_{el}/t. It is expected that the costs of the electricity required will at least halve over the next two decades.²⁸

5.2 Sequestration in the pore space of sedimentary rocks

Storage of CO₂ under high pressure in the geological bedrock is already being carried out, whereby we reject the technology of Enhanced Gas Recovery / Enhanced Oil Recovery. Below we give an overview of the projects running in various countries.

In Germany, a pilot experiment on CO₂ sequestration – the only onshore CO₂ storage project to date in Europe – was carried out in Ketzin under the leadership of the German Research Center for Geosciences (GFZ, 2023). From 2008 to 2013, a total of 67 271 tonnes of CO₂ (0.000067271 Gt) were stored. The storage took place in the pore space of a sandstone layer at a depth of 630–650 m, which is sealed by an overlying layer of claystone.

In Norway, CO₂ has been stored in the seabed since 1996 (Norwegian Petroleum, n.d.). In the *Sleipner* project (Scinexx, 2016) 0.0155 Gt CO₂ have been stored so far, and from 2024 around 0.005 Gt CO₂ per year will be added. Here the CO₂ is also stored in sandstone under an impermeable top layer at a depth of 800 m.

In Denmark, the *Greensand* project began in March 2023 to press CO₂ into a former oil field in the North Sea about 200 km off the coast (Greensand, n.d.). In 2025/2026, up to 0.0015 Gt CO₂/year should be stored, and by 2030 the capacity should be increased to up to 0.008 Gt CO₂/year (Reuters, 2023).

In the Netherlands, from 2024 onwards, 0.0025 Gt/year of CO₂ emitted by industry is to be stored in empty gas fields under the North Sea in the *Porthos* project (Port of Rotterdam, 2021). The UK has announced it will spend twenty billion pounds on CCS over the next twenty years. In the UK, 19 % of the emissions reductions should come from a combination of carbon capture and removal by 2050, according to the Climate Change Committee, a government advisory body. The British government has already set a target of removing at least 0.005 Gt of greenhouse gases per year through technical measures by 2030 and storing 0.02–0.03 Gt of CO₂/year by 2050 (Williams, 2023). Also, Canada hopes to store at least 0.015 Gt CO₂/year by 2030 (Tsafos & Naimoli, 2022). Worldwide, the projects that have been carried out or are specifically

²⁸ Over the last 40 years, the doubling of solar module production capacity has been accompanied by a 25% reduction in manufacturing costs (Fraunhofer Institute for Solar Energy Systems, 2023).

planned to date are still far from the scale required: According to the IEA, 0.044 Gt of CO₂ was captured worldwide in 2021 (IEA, n.d.).

The existing global storage capacities for CO₂ would be more than sufficient: in Germany alone, there is space for 9 to 16 Gt of CO₂ – a multiple of Germany’s total annual emissions – in porous rocks (especially sandstone in the North German Basin and former natural gas deposits), according to calculations by the Federal Institute for Geosciences and Natural Resources (BGR, 2010). However, conflicts of use must be taken into account when storing, especially on land, because various conceivable types of use of the underground (e. g. geothermal energy in the classic sense, but also as heat storage underground, gas storage or resource extraction through mining) are mutually exclusive. An underground development plan would be useful here.²⁹

Fig. 11: Capacities for CO₂ sequestration in the pore space of sedimentary rocks in Europe (Heinrich-Böll-Stiftung/Bund für Umwelt und Naturschutz Deutschland, 2015, CC BY-SA 3.0 DE).

²⁹ It is also stated in the evaluation report of the Federal Government for the Carbon Dioxide Storage Law (KSpG) (Bundesregierung, 2022, 70) "that a multi-storey use of the underground as well as a superimposition of various underground uses with near-surface uses and functions appears to be fundamentally (geo-)technically possible if the individual uses/functions are compatible with each other. The legal framework for this and for taking such possible uses into account in (underground) spatial planning must be examined and, if necessary, developed."

Outside Germany, storage capacities are significantly higher. For the Norwegian part of the North Sea alone, a capacity of 70–100 Gt is estimated (Norwegian Offshore Directorate, 2022; Wallmann, n.d.; see also Fig. 11), i.e. around 6 % of the negative emissions required worldwide to reduce the CO₂ concentration to 350 ppm. Total global storage capacity is estimated at 8 000–55 000 Gt (Malischek & McCulloch, 2021). Even if only part of it is practical, accessible and close to the emitters, these figures make it clear that there is more than sufficient capacity worldwide.

The price for CO₂ sequestration in the pore space of sedimentary rocks would decrease with larger systems (scaling effects) and, like the price of storage in basaltic rocks, is highly dependent on the energy price. In a commentary published by the International Energy Agency (IEA), Baylin-Stern & Berghout (2021) estimate that costs vary from case to case, but under current economic and technical conditions they could often be less than 10 US \$/t (for storage only). In addition, the costs for transport are of a similar magnitude. Storage offshore increases costs by a further approximately 10 US \$/t (under today's conditions; Schmelz et al., 2020).

5.3 Possible dangers of CO₂ storage in the pore space of sedimentary rocks underwater and on land

The pilot project in Ketzin yielded relevant insights into the dangers of sequestration on land: In summary, it emerged that CO₂ sequestration can be implemented safely and reliably in Germany and without endangering people and the environment. This results from the following points:

(1) No leakage was detected in Ketzin. The integrity of the bedding and cover rocks was not affected (GFZ, 2023). The geological formations in Ketzin are similar to those in which storage on a larger scale would be possible (GFZ, n.d.) – namely sandstones that are sealed by an overlying layer. Therefore, the results are spatially highly scalable. Although this experiment only ran for several years, modelling predicts that no CO₂ would escape even over much longer periods of time (Liebscher et al., 2012). Rather, it dissolves in the salty groundwater and ideally reacts in such a way that it bonds firmly to the rock (it becomes carbonate). When stored in gaseous form under high pressure, half of the CO₂ is expected to be dissolved in water after 1 000 years; after 10 000 years, one third of the CO₂ is mineralized and is then in solid form (IPCC, 2005).

(2) There is also experience with gas storage facilities in which no leakage was recorded, even over long periods of time, i.e. all gas leaks that occurred could be traced back to avoidable technical defects and did not occur due to the geological subsoil.

(3) Natural gas and oil deposits remain stable underground for millions of years. If CO₂ is stored in the same or comparable formations, it can be expected that it will be stored just as stably. However, differences in the behaviour of CO₂ compared to oil and gas, e. g. in terms of solubility in water, must again be taken into account through experiments and modelling.

A slightly larger CO₂ sequestration project (3.8 Mt = 0.0038 Gt), which was also accompanied by monitoring and modelling, was carried out in In Salah in Algeria (Rin-

grose et al., 2013). Oldenburg et al. (2010) find an overall low risk of leakage for this project but recommend ongoing modelling and monitoring of the injection process. White et al. (2014) find for this project, despite cracks in the rock, there is no evidence that the entire storage complex has been compromised, and several independent data sets demonstrate that CO₂ is contained in the confinement zone. A report by Hauber (2023) from the Institute for Energy Economics and Financial Analysis, however, emphasizes the problems of the two CCS projects *Sleipner* and *Snøhvit*. The greatest uncertainty lies in the casing and cementation, i.e. the connection between the surface and the deposit (Alcalde et al., 2021). There is no experience over a period of 1 000 years or more with the behaviour of boreholes when permanently exposed to carbon dioxide (Goerne et al., 2010). This also applies to boreholes planned to be resistant to carbon dioxide. Scientific studies on possible leaks from CO₂ sequestration in former natural gas and oil fields in the North Sea clearly come to the conclusion that leaks represent a risk (Vielstädte et al., 2019). CO₂ leaks are not easy to detect because CO₂ dissolves very quickly in seawater, as has been proven in controlled experiments. Only a permanent CO₂ leak from numerous boreholes threatens to limit the effectiveness of storage. Vielstädte et al. (2019) therefore point out that areas with a high density of former wells may not always be the most suitable areas for CO₂ storage. Leakage would not only undermine the effectiveness of storage but would also have local environmental impacts as the composition of the community of living creatures and important ecological functions would permanently change under high CO₂ levels (Molari et al., 2018).

As mentioned, some states bordering the North Sea have already started storing CO₂. The greatest possible safety of pipelines for CO₂ transport must be guaranteed. After each storage of CO₂, monitoring is necessary to be able to measure any increase in escaping CO₂. It must be taken into account that CO₂ escapes from the underground even without human intervention. CO₂ is heavier than air and can therefore accumulate in depressions, basements, etc. It is colourless and odourless and, although non-toxic, is suffocating; In extreme cases it can lead to death due to lack of oxygen. However, the risk can be classified as low. Natural CO₂ must be measured before storage in order to quantify that there is no measurably significant increase after storage. On land, the measurements are so precise that even a very small increase – compared to dangerous or harmful concentrations – can be measured. Other possible dangers that play a role particularly in sequestration on land and which must be eliminated as far as possible through appropriate investigations, modelling and precautions include the triggering of local earthquakes and the acidification of groundwater. Earthquakes could be triggered because CO₂ is injected under pressure, creating stresses in the rock that exceed its strength. When CO₂ comes into contact with groundwater, it can react to form carbonic acid, leading to acidification. Overall, the conclusion can be drawn “that CCS is fundamentally assessed by science as a low-risk, controllable technology.” (Erlach et al., 2022, 6). And the Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Protection also writes: “Suitable geological reservoirs are, for example, depleted oil or natural gas deposits and rock layers containing salt water (so-called *saline aquifers*). Large amounts of CO₂ can be injected into

these reservoirs and stored safely over geological time periods” (Bundesministerium für Wirtschaft und Klimaschutz, 2024).

As an accompanying measure – as with other climate protection measures – the population must be involved in the implementation of this technology. In the pilot project in Ketzin, this happened, among other things, by setting up a visitor centre. This had the effect that local citizens and members of the city parliament got an impression of how great the international attention was for the project. Important stakeholders were actively involved, such as the fire department, which would have had to respond in the event of a technical accident. Future CDR projects would have to be based on these measures.

You can only win the acceptance of the population if you provide clear and detailed information to the public before the start and, if necessary, set up committees that include citizens who are involved in all steps. Monitoring must be guaranteed transparently so that citizens have access to the monitor data. As with other mining projects, an ESHIA (Environmental Social and Health Impact Assessment) would be necessary, i.e. a study that may run over several years and includes, among other things, large-scale tests with monitoring. The BGR would have to create maps and studies directly about potential final repositories for CO₂. Every mining project involves risks, but these can be sufficiently mitigated if they are identified. Shortcuts to the process should be strictly avoided here, otherwise there is a risk of loss of acceptance.

6. The amendment to the Carbon Dioxide Storage Act (KSpG)

Due to the *Carbon Dioxide Storage Act* of 2012, CO₂ sequestration is prohibited in Germany, except for testing purposes.³⁰ An evaluation report from the federal government found in 2022 that the law was outdated. Points of criticism were, for example:

“In the course of this evaluation report on the KSpG, it was found that the current legal framework conflicts with the specific application of CCS and CCU in practice. The approval of CO₂ pipelines for the purpose of CCU is not legally possible. At the same time, the climate neutrality studies analysed in the report see these technologies in different degrees as part of a strategy to achieve the greenhouse gas neutrality for Germany set out in the Climate Protection Act by 2045.” (Federal Government, 2022, 138) “Section 2 Paragraph 5 KSpG (“State Clause”), in addition, gives the federal states the opportunity to designate or exclude areas for CO₂ storage. Some federal states have used this option to exclude storage throughout their entire territory.” (Federal Government, 2022, 142).

An amendment to the law is currently being discussed, according to current reports, however, only a lifting of the export ban appears to be politically feasible for the time being, which would mean that sequestration would remain prohibited in Germany it-

³⁰ The deadline for registering projects for test purposes has also long passed.

self (Götze et al., 2023). However, if the voices that demand the adoption of a comprehensive CCS strategy before amending this law prevail, then this amendment to the law will be put on the back burner. However, time is the decisive factor in limiting the damage caused by climate change. Even if an expansion of sequestration on the necessary scale is not expected until the 2040s, a testing, preparation and decision-making phase is necessary until then. The project in Ketzin was very small-scale. In order to ensure that storage in the geological subsurface is possible and low-risk, appropriate medium-scale field tests are the next, necessary step.

For safety reasons, Germany should aim to ensure that the CO₂ produced in this country that is to be stored is only stored in countries with high safety standards. Such standards could and should be established in Germany. The transport route to German North Sea territorial waters would be relatively short. This would also mean that the transport costs would be comparatively low, with sufficient capacity available. The export of Germany's CO₂ to Norwegian territory for underwater sequestration, which is currently being discussed, is also to be advocated and makes sense from a climate protection perspective, after all Norway has a much larger share of the suitable storage area under the North Sea compared to the population. On the other hand, there is the argument that each country should, if possible, use sequestration sites for its own CO₂.

7. Synthesis and outlook

To limit global warming to 1°C above pre-industrial levels in the long term, a new, more active phase of climate policy is necessary. Even if the current CO₂ concentrations in the atmosphere are maintained for a longer period of time, there is a risk of tipping elements and irreversible changes to the Earth system being triggered. It is therefore desirable to reduce the atmospheric CO₂ concentration from today's around 424 ppm to 350 ppm. This is a new phase in climate policy in which the goal of quickly achieving negative emissions becomes the second branch of the global climate strategy alongside the priority of implementing emissions avoidance as quickly as possible. In the first step, a very rapid reduction in further new CO₂ emissions (currently just under 40 Gt annually and rising) is required.

We need 100 % renewable energy worldwide. At the same time, the conditions must be created today so that negative emissions in the gigatonne range can be achieved in the near future. Such remissions can be achieved with plant-based solutions (BECCS) and technical processes such as DACCS. CO₂ removal and storage through technical processes is currently still expensive and energy-intensive, but the alternative of doing nothing is much more expensive in the longer term and may even threaten the existence of humanity. Massive investments, primarily from non-state actors, could reduce the costs of direct air capture and carbon capture at industrial facilities; the same applies to CO₂ sequestration in the geological bedrock (which is currently still banned in Germany). Biological methods are financially cheaper but are associated with significant problems when used on a large scale. It is currently not possible to conclusively estimate which combination of negative emission methods will ulti-

mately prevail. Due to the urgency of the task, we believe it is wrong to exclude individual methods from the outset.

8. Literature

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Keywords: Negative Emissions, Carbon Dioxide Removal (CDR), Direct Air Carbon Capture and Sequestration (DACCS), Bioenergy Carbon Capture and Sequestration (BECCS), Climate Ethics, Climate Duties, net emissions, German Carbon Dioxide Storage Act

Role of the authors: Jörg Tremmel and Bernhard Steinberger were lead authors. The other authors each made topic-specific technical contributions and checked the text for consistency and correctness. All authors participated in several online discussions and edited the text together.

Acknowledgements: We benefited from feedback from (in alphabetical order): Ottmar Edenhofer, Oliver Geden, Katharina Theis-Bröhl and Ernst Ulrich von Weizsäcker

This text was written by scientists who are involved in "Scientists for Future" and represents the views of the authors, but not of all scientists active in Scientists for Future.

The editors of the publication series "Discussion contributions from Scientists for Future" are: Claus-Heinrich Daub, Kirsten von Elverfeldt, Gregor Hagedorn, Clara Herdeanu, Sven Linow, Bernhard Steinberger and Christina West. Editors who are also authors do not participate in decisions about publication. Publication guidelines are available at doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10402844. Editor and proofreader: Kirsten von Elverfeldt.

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Diskussionsbeiträge der Scientists for Future

- 1: (Die erste Stellungnahme 2019 wurde als Nummer 1 der Diskussionsbeiträge gewertet: doi: [10.14512/gaia.28.2.3](https://doi.org/10.14512/gaia.28.2.3))
 - 2: (Version 1.1 der folgenden Publikation aus dem Jahr 2019, siehe doi: [10.5281/zenodo.3371150](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3371150))
 - 3: Mattauch, L., Creutzig, F., Moore, N. aus dem, Franks, M., Funke, F., Jakob, M., Sager, L., Schwarz, M., Voß, A., Beck, M.-L., Daub, C.-H., Drupp, M., Ekardt, F., Hagedorn, G., Kirchner, M., Kruse, T., Loew, T., Neuhoff, K., Neuweg, I., ... Wallacher, J. (2020). Antworten auf zentrale Fragen zur Einführung von CO₂-Preisen (Version 2.0) – Gestaltungsoptionen und ihre Auswirkungen für den schnellen Übergang in die klimafreundliche Gesellschaft. *Diskussionsbeiträge der Scientists for Future*, 3, 1–41. doi: [10.5281/zenodo.3644498](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3644498)
 - 4: (Version 1.0 der folgenden Publikation, siehe doi: [10.5281/zenodo.4311486](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4311486))
 - 5: Hagedorn, G., Baasch, S., Blöbaum, A., Brendel, H., Hardt, J. N., Heiland, S., Klinsmann, M., Matthies, E., Pfennig, A., West, C., Wipfler, B., Altermatt, P. P., Baumgarten, S., Bergmann, M., Brendel, E., van Bronswijk, K., Creutzig, F., Daub, C.-H., Dohm, L., ... Weber, U. (2021). Scientists for Future empfiehlt eine repräsentative Klima-Bürger:innenversammlung im Jahr 2021 / Scientists for Future recommends a representative Climate Citizens' Assembly in 2021 (Version 1.1). *Diskussionsbeiträge der Scientists for Future*, 5, 1–23. doi: [10.5281/zenodo.4417265](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4417265)
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- Buch: „Die Wärmewende“ / Policy-Paper Wärmewende**
- Clausen, J., Seifert, T., & Huber, M., (Hrsg.). (2024). *Die Wärmewende. Zentrale Aufgabe einer klimaverantwortlichen Kommunalpolitik*. Scientists for Future, Berlin, 160 Seiten.
- Das Buch basiert auf acht zwischen 2022 und 2023 publizierten „Policy-Paper Wärmewende“, welche – inhaltlich aktualisiert und unter teilweise aufgrund der Überarbeitung geänderter Autorenschaft – hier zusammengefasst wurden. Nach Möglichkeit sollte diese aktualisierte Fassung von 2024 verwendet werden. Die im Buch aktualisierten Originalpublikationen sind:
- 1: Clausen, J., Ehrhardt, H., Huber, M., Linow, S., Seifert, T., Beisheim, M. (2022). Heizen mit Holz: knapp, teuer und unerwartet klimaschädlich. *Policy-Paper Wärmewende*, 01-2022. info-de.scientists4future.org/wp-content/uploads/sites/36/2022/07/Policy_Paper_01_HeizenmitHolz.pdf

(Some Publications by Scientists for Future)

- 2: Clausen, J., Johannsen, L., Böhler, H., Kranich, K., Huber, M., Seifert, T. (2022). Kommunale Wärmeplanung. Grundlage einer klimaverantwortlichen Stadtplanung. *Policy-Paper Wärmewende, 02-2022*. info-de.scientists4future.org/wp-content/uploads/sites/36/2023/01/Policy_Paper_02_Waermewende.pdf
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 - 2: Clausen, J., Altermatt, P., Ehrhardt, H., Gerhards, C., Golla, S., Guthke, R., Huber, M., Jordan, U., Kemfert, C., Kopeck, J., Kranich, K., Linow, S., Miara, M., Quaschnig, V., Sanders, A., Seifert, T., Stelzer, V., Tvrtković, M., Vogt, T., Windmüller, P. & Zosseder, K. (2023). Die schnelle Verbreitung der Wärmepumpe ist zentral für eine schnelle Wärmewende. Online-Publikation, Berlin. Scientists for Future. 7 Seiten. doi: [10.5281/zenodo.8003360](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8003360) (AUCH: info-de.scientists4future.org/wp-content/uploads/sites/36/2023/06/S4F-Schnelle_Verbreitung_Waermepumpe_-_Clausen_et_al._2023.pdf)
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- 1: Engelbrecht, H., Priester, M., Rechlin, A. (2023). Nachhaltigkeitsaspekte der Urangewinnung. Anmerkungen zur Taxonomie-Entscheidung der EU. Keypoint Papier Kernkraft 01 (de). info-de.scientists4future.org/wp-content/uploads/sites/36/2023/03/Keypoint_Paper_KKW.pdf
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- Facetten des Zukunftsbilder-Projekts**
- (Mit Stand 2024-03-28 wurden 29 Facetten der Zukunftsbilder publiziert. Diese sind hier aufgeführt: zenodo.org/communities/zukunftsbilder/records. Das Zukunftsbilderprojekt betreibt zudem die Website zukunftsbilder.net.)